

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH READING*Sh. Ashurova*¹*Abstract:*

Students usually get difficulties in learning English subject. Especially for reading section. Teaching reading is not as simple as people think. They should have any more practice and should enlarge their knowledge to deliver reading materials especially at school children. Researchers found that the English teachers used interesting methods that students can learn about reading tests in a good condition. This comprehensive article explain what methods students should use and how they can learn better.

Key words: vocabulary, reading strategies, speed-reading techniques, comprehension, scanning and skimming methods.

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English one of the most widely spoken languages in almost all the countries. Although English language is challenge, everyone who learns English wants to speak English fluently. English is included four skills which are speaking, writing, listening and reading. Reading is considered as important part of language; it helps not only in speaking but also in the developing of the other part of English language. What is reading. Reading is about understanding written texts. It is complex activity that involves both perception and thought. Reading consists of two related processes; word recognition and comprehension. In this article, the author considers the importance of reading in the study, reading methods and introduce various strategies in teaching reading.

Scientists and linguists who study language and live modern world give the following definitions to the term “reading” the connection between the reader and the text. In addition, other scientists agree that good readers must do some other things to understand the text well, they must connect new text to the past experience or as it might be called background knowledge. Many scientists have conducted research for the development of reading. The first method is to choose reading materials at their level. A big part of getting students to learn English from reading is being able to select materials that are a good fit for their reading level.

Reading research

There are some methods, sometimes known as the New Methods or the Reading Approach, was devised by Dr. Michael Phillip West. During the 1920s, he was working as a Professor of English in India. He was a respected educator, his beliefs found a following. The Reading Method became widely used to teach French and German to American children. The Reading Method also gained in the UK as a way of teaching children who were struggling with their linguistic development.

At the time when the Dr. West was working, the most popular method of teaching English to students in other countries was the Direct Method also

¹*Shoira Ashurova, student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

known as the Natural Method. This method focused heavily on spoken words through students actively participating in class. They were encouraged to learn English words directly without translating them into their first language. Dr. West thought this method was too time-consuming as a lot of class time taken up with the teacher talking, so each student didn't get much time to practice their speaking skills. He stated that people needed minimum of 1158 words to be able to express their ideas in a normal conversation, and he categorized these words into two different types.

1. Form words — these are the grammatical words which connect ideas and form the building blocks of English.

2. Content word — these are the words we use to talk and express ourselves.

When it came to reading, Dr. West believed that minimum number of words you needed to be able to read and understand was 2280. Again, he divided these words into different categories.

1. Essential words (“a”, “is”, “it”, “that”)

2. Common environmental words (“house”, “car”, “table”, “cup”)

3. General words (“good”, “bad”)

4. Specific environmental words (“trees”, “flowers”, “sea”, “mountains”)

Using the Reading Method, these 2280 words would be introduced gradually to students and learned via a lot of repetition.

What are advantages of reading method in English teaching

The Reading Method was almost totally focused on students reading individually and silently. Dr. West also thought that silent reading helped students to concentrate and absorb the material more efficiently, improving their comprehension.

What are the disadvantages of the reading method?

The Reading Method limits students' vocabulary to the 2280 words that Dr. West thought were essential to learning to read English and also students do not learn any idioms or do any writing composition under the Reading Method, this makes it difficult for them to learn how to express themselves.

Some research by author

I explored a method in order to improve the reading. If the students do not have enough experience to read, they should do some practice.

— Reduces stress and help you relax

— Improves your concentration and memory

— Improves your vocabulary and strengthens your writing abilities

— Enhances your knowledge

— Increase your imagination and creativity

— Read some small journals to comprehend the text

When the students read some texts, they should try to understand the meaning of text by heart. In addition, if they come across a word which is unknown for reader, they should predict the word from general meaning of the text. Some students cannot concentrate on the text during the reading and do not understand the text well even after reading it several times. At such a time, students must concentrate on the text. In addition, it is recommended to develop their imagination, they will better understand the events in the text.

For many years, comprehension in only reasons for reading. Without comprehension, reading is a frustrating, pointless exercise in word calling. It is also exaggeration to say that how well students develop the ability to comprehend what they read has a profound effect on their entire lives.

Comprehension introduction followed what they study a called mentoring, practicing and assessing procedure where teachers mentioned a specific skill by completing work book page it is plausible that preparation in the nature of the foundational reading skills and research based instructional approaches would improve teacher's practice to a degree that would be evident in earning outcomes for their students.

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